

Table 2. Growth and yield of rice as influenced by seed rate (A), seed density (B), and N fertilizer (C) under natural submergence (S1) and simulated flashflooding (S2) at Cuttack, India, during 1994 (Experiment 2).

Treatment	Seedling emergence (%)	Plant height (cm)		Panicles m ⁻² (no.)		Panicle weight (g)		Grain yield (tha ⁻¹)		Straw yield (tha ⁻¹)	
		S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2
Seed rate (m⁻²)											
400	32.3	125	112	77	67	2.88	2.16	2.5	1.7	4.7	2.7
600	30.9	129	113	82	79	2.71	2.08	2.4	1.9	5.4	3.0
Seed density (mg)											
19.4	29.8	126	112	74	68	2.53	2.07	2.3	1.6	4.9	2.4
22.9	33.4	128	113	85	78	3.06	2.17	2.5	1.9	5.3	3.2
N fertilizer (kg ha⁻¹)											
0	31.5	125	107	76	64	2.68	2.02	2.2	1.6	4.4	2.3
40	3.18	129	118	83	82	2.91	2.27	2.6	2.0	5.6	3.2
Mean	-	127	111	80	73	2.80	2.10	2.4	1.8	5.0	2.8
CD (0.05)											
Submergence level			13		ns		1		0.33		2.05
Mean effects of A, B, or C	3.0		5		5		2		1		1
Interaction (S X A, B, or C) ^b			6		7		7		0.15		2

^a Same variety and natural conditions as in Table 1. Simulated flashflooding was done in especially constructed tanks at 90±2 cm depth for 10 d continuously at 75 d of growth. ^b Interaction between A, B, and C was not significant.

intervals during the second week of June. These conditions resulted in delayed and very poor germination (<35%). Seedling emergence 25 d after sowing was significantly higher in high-density seeds, but percent emergence from different seed rates or N fertilizer levels were similar (Tables 1 and 2).

Plants raised from dense seeds appeared more vigorous and suffered less from the initial drought. Water built up from the last week of June and rose rapidly to 30 cm at 18 d after seedling emergence (DE) and 70 cm at 34 DE. Subsequent flooding completely submerged plants for about a week. However, the relatively taller and vigorous rice plants raised from high-density seeds and with N fertilizer application showed better recovery after the flood receded. Natural flooding up to 82 cm at the end of August also submerged most plants for more than 10 d. Experiment 2 also subjected the crop to simulated flashflooding at the beginning of September for 10 d, after which the floodwater receded gradually.

At crop maturity, the plants from high-density seeds were taller, but seed rates made no significant difference (Table 1). Artificial flashflooding re-

duced plant height significantly more than natural submergence (Table 2). The ability of N fertilizer to increase plant height was more pronounced under flashflooding conditions.

In experiment 1, mean grain yield remained unaffected by increased seed rate because an increase in number of panicles m⁻² at a higher seed rate was associated with reduced panicle weight (Table 1). Interaction comparison revealed that yield increased significantly with increasing seed density, particularly at the lower seed rates of 200 and 400 seeds m⁻². Grain yield increased up to 600 seeds m⁻² with the use of low-density seeds, but the effect from using medium- and high-density seeds at varying rates was similar. This result suggests that seed rate can be reduced by using high-density seeds. Vigorous seedlings not only establish well but survive better under drought or flooding; also, plants compensate for the poor crop stand at the lower seed rate through increased tillering.

In experiment 2, the beneficial effects of seed rate, seed density, and N fertilizer were more pronounced under simulated flashflooding than under natural submergence (Table 2). The mean increase in yield from N fertilizer, high-density seeds, and higher seed

rate was 25.2, 20.9, and 11.8%, respectively under simulated flashflooding conditions. Higher seed rate did not affect yield under natural submergence, but instead yield increased by 15.7 and 8.7% using N fertilizer and high-density seeds. The greater beneficial effect of N and high-density seeds was associated with a greater number and weight of panicles. Mean grain yield decreased 25.7% by flashflooding compared with natural submergence, but similar reductions in yield were less with the use of 40 kg N ha⁻¹ (22.9%), high-density seeds (21.6%), and higher seed rate (19.9%) than without N (28.7%), low-density seed (29.9%), and normal seed rate (30.4%), respectively.

We conclude that yield performance of flood-prone lowland rice depends largely on initial crop stand and vigor, which can be improved by using a higher seed rate and plump seeds with basal fertilization. High-density seeds germinate better and produce vigorous seedlings, leading to greater survival under initial drought and flashflooding. These abiotic stresses can also be mitigated by increasing the seed rate and N fertilizer. ■

Effect of tillage and fertilizer levels on grain yield and incidence of brown spot disease in rice

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This study was done in kharif 1992 and 1993 at Pantnagar to observe the effect of tillage practices and fertilizer levels on rice production and disease incidence. A split-plot design was used with puddled 'P' and unpuddled 'UP' as main plots and two fertilizer levels as subplots of 11.8 × 6.0 m. Fertilizer levels were F₁: 120 kg N ha⁻¹, 17 kg P ha⁻¹, and

33 kg K ha⁻¹ and F₂: 100 kg N ha⁻¹, 26 kg P ha⁻¹, and 50 kg K-ha⁻¹. In 'UP' plots, the seeds of cv Pant Dhan 4 were drilled in 20 cm rows on 20 Jun 1992 and 3 Jul 1993, and in P plots 30-d-old seedlings were transplanted on 23 Jul 1992 and 7 Jul 1993 with a spacing of 20 × 15 cm. Phosphorus and potash were given basally and N was applied in three splits, 50% P and 25% UP as basal; 25% P and 50% UP at tillering; and 25% (P and UP) at panicle initiation.

Disease incidence was recorded on five stools selected at random from each plot according to IRRI's 1988 *Standard evaluation system for rice*. The number of shoots at harvest was 360 m⁻² (1992) and 390 m⁻² (1993) in UP plots compared with 280 m⁻² (1992) and 270 m⁻² (1993) in P plots. Incidence of brown spot caused by *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* (Ito and Kuribayashi) Drechsler ex Dastur anamorph *Drechslera oryzae* (Breda de Hann) Subra and Jain was severe in both seasons. Fertility levels had no significant effect on the severity of brown spot, while tillage significantly

Disease and grain yield (t ha⁻¹) in puddled (P) and unpuddled plots (UP) at two fertilizer levels. Pantnagar, India, 1992 and 1993.

Treatment	Brown spot disease (%) ^a		Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	1992	1993	1992	1993
120 kg N + 17 kg P + 33 kg K ha ⁻¹ (P)	19.54 (26.21)	22.2 (28.1)	5.3	5.8
100 kg N + 26 kg P + 50 kg K ha ⁻¹ (P)	17.05 (24.73)	19.4 (26.13)	6.6	6.1
120 kg N + 17 kg P + 33 kg K ha ⁻¹ (UP)	30.05 (33.21)	52.7 (46.55)	4.8	4.9
100 kg N + 26 kg P + 50 kg K ha ⁻¹ (UP)	29.43 (32.43)	44.4 (41.78)	5.2	5.8
CD (5%) Tillage	4.33	0.86	0.4	1.7
Fertility	ns	ns	0.4	1.7
CV	18.48	26.5	10.0	5.0

^aFigures in parentheses are angular values.

influenced it. The disease index was significantly lower in P than in UP plots, and the difference more pronounced in 1993 (see table).

During kharif 1992, yield was significantly higher in both P and UP plots. The yield was also higher in P than in UP plots. In 1993, however, treatment effects were not significant. The severity of brown spot increased

significantly in UP plots, an effect attributable to their higher plant population. Another reason may be the poor water management in UP plots with nutritional imbalance in the soil that aggravates the disease. Caution must be exercised in recommending the cultivation of rice in UP fields, because brown spot may become a limiting factor. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Effect of submergence of rice plants on the development of sheath blight

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During the monsoon season, heavy and continuous rainfall keeps plants under water for extended periods of time. We studied the impact of submergence on sheath blight (ShB) infection in rice.

Plants of a highly susceptible rice cultivar, Annapurna, were grown in pots well supplied with fertilizer. When the plants were at flowering stage, leaf sheaths of the second youngest leaves in each of three tillers per plant were inoculated with a sterilized rice "stem" piece colonized by the causal fungus, *Rhizoctonia solani* Kühn.

Three days after inoculation, grayish-green lesions measuring 3.0-3.5 cm developed on the inoculated tillers. The inoculum was gently removed with sterilized forceps, and the plants were submerged to establish lesions. The plants were removed from water at intervals and placed in a glasshouse. Three replications were maintained for each treatment. On the 14th d after inoculation, lesions on each inoculated tiller was measured at the same time with leaf infection and sclerotia produced.

Results indicated that submergence of the infected plants greatly reduced the development of ShB (see table). Disease continued to develop in plants that were under water for 2 d, but beyond that period we observed a sudden and strong decrease in the progress of infection. Disease develop-

Development of ShB infection in rice plants subjected to submergence, Cuttack, India, 1996 WS.

Duration of submergence (d)	Mean lesion length (cm)	Extent of leaf infection ^a	Sclerotia produced (no.)
0	38.7	++	18
2	28.2	++	5
4	12.3	+	3
6	6.7	-	0
8	4.0	-	0
10	3.7	-	0
Continuous submergence	No further infection		
Control (no submergence)	45.5	+++	26
CD for treatments			
5% = 5.1			
1% = 7.1			

^a- = none, + = slight, ++ = moderate, +++ = severe.

ment in 6, 8, and 10-d submergence treatments was significantly lower than in 0, 2, and 4-d treatments. Almost no